

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUFUNDA****FIRST NAME: FORTUNATE****PROGRAM CODE : DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay writing (Cleenwerck and Gulma 2021, 7-14; Turabian 2018, 56-126)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenwerck and Gulma 2021, 34-39; Turabian 2018, 81-83)
3. Style guide (Cleenwerck and Gulma 2021, 41-42)
4. The Chicago Manual of Style (Cleenwerck and Gulma 2021, 44-53)
5. Language (Cleenwerck and Gulma, 2021, 25-32)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

In this free response paper, I will give an overview of my understanding of the course, having accessed the video presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenwerck and the ACA-401 reading material done by Prof. Laurent Cleenwerck and Dr Gulma. At first, I needed to understand a free response paper, having missed it in my initial submission as I had not read the orientation document. Nevertheless, I had to rewatch the video and read the ACA-401D orientation booklet several times to understand.

In this essay, I will discuss the key concepts learnt in my initial steps to becoming a PhD holder at Euclid University. My writing language will be British (UK) English as that has been the official language in my home country, which I have used in my entire education life and more so as a home second language. I will dwell on five concepts: essay writing, plagiarism, punctuation, a style guide, and American or British English.

2) **ESSAY WRITING**

I have understood in this course how necessary it is to plan before drafting an academic essay. Having worked as a researcher and done a few published scientific research papers, I needed to retrain myself in some concepts of writing that had almost become inborn and probably unacceptable. The writing tips outlined in the ACA-401D course pack and the Turabian manual guide assisted me a lot in understanding the academic essay writing process again.

The essay writing process includes drafting a clear plan with stated questions or objectives. Essay questions or objectives, as I understood and experienced, can take several times to convince oneself, followed by researching widely on the topic by reading a wide array of sources in detail and skimming through for critical terms. Moreover, during the literature search, I understood how taking notes and excerpts and writing down source details (creating a reference list) is essential; missed facts can lead to failure to cite or attribute the content to its rightful source.

The writing process eventually begins with drafting an introduction, body, and conclusion. The essay should state right in the beginning the purpose of the writing to entice the reader to read further. Several attempts at it will eventually result in an article well laid out with structure, a logical flow of content with cited and referenced works, and precise answers to questions posed in the initial plan of the essay. The drafted essay should be revised before finalisation and submission (Cleenwerck and Gulma 2021, 8).

In so much as scientific writing is meant to present findings based on evidence, I concur that it also requires the same attention. It is therefore done in a structured way where data is presented, previous findings are referenced, and the contribution of the new body of information is explained. Scientific writing is based on a working hypothesis (claim) with supporting evidence from the researcher's work or previous studies to answer the questions raised initially (Turabian 2018, 136).

In this response paper, I recap the main concepts I have read in the ACA-401D course pack, the Turabian Rule of Style, and the Vimeo video I watched.

a) Plagiarism

Webster (2023) defines the plagiarising act as “stealing and passing off (the ideas or words of another) as one's own: use (another's production) without crediting the source”. In this paragraph, I will discuss ways to ensure adequate reference of other researchers' work is properly cited. Unavoidably I argue that plagiarism may happen unknowingly, and a certain percentage is acceptable, less than 18% (EUCLID 2021). Citing work unnecessarily where the context is a general phenomenon is also considered plagiarism. How a writer presents their work will largely depend on their field, that is, scientific or other where that can dictate preferential use of quoting or paraphrasing citation method.

i) Quotation marks

These are used where a phrase shows originality, and a borrowed sentence for which putting the idea in own words would fail to portray the meaning. The quotes can be preceded by signal verbs (Turabian 2018, 371; Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 36). A section with a few sentences should be formatted using the Word-style menu.

ii) Paraphrasing

I agree that paraphrasing is when the cited work is expressed in the writer's own words, and appropriate parentheses refer to the source of the idea. Turabian (2018, 376) considers rephrasing too closely and failure to discern regular or commonly used expressions as a grey area that can naively be cited and subsequently saves the writer the pain of a plagiarising charge.

b) Punctuation

Webster (2023) defines punctuation as "the act or practice of inserting standardised marks or signs in a written matter to clarify the meaning and separate structural units". Cleenwerck and Gulma (2021,16) recommend minimal use of punctuation to retain the meaning of a sentence and strive to use short meaningful sentences. However, I believe that using commas, apostrophes, colons or semicolons, and brackets can change the purpose of a sentence but may be very necessary to clarify a point. Punctuations are also used differently in the UK compared to US English.

c) Style Guide

The EUCLID (2021) standard referencing style guide of choice is *Turabian Style (author-date)* as the citation method. Turabian is adapted from the Chicago Manual of Style writing techniques and has had several revisions by various editors, the latest being the 9th edition of 2018. The citation method per ACA-401 course pack is 'in text' *author and date*. As Cleenwerck and Gulma (2021, 41) clearly explain:

"A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that must be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent. So guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the writer's style but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with many contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent".

Style guide may also be specific to a field such as in the mandatory use of the World Health Organisation Referencing style by public health specialists.

d) Referencing Software

Referencing style and referencing software are now considered hand in glove to a writer. In this work, I have used Zotero referencing software, which has become standard in writing in any field to use a referencing software. The Zotero referencing software makes accumulating a library of material read and keeping notes easier than handwritten lists, which must be typed in. Whilst it is a good referencing software, editing information in Zotero and after insertion in an essay is imperative. Within Zotero, the writing language and the style guide are set, so it becomes systematic when citations are inputted into the article. Entries to Zotero can be done manually using a web URL or source identifier, even though correcting the information remains necessary.

e) Chicago Manual of Style (CMS)

In so much as the Turabian style of writing has been discussed, it is also necessary to give an ear to the originating style, the CMS. As Cleenwerck and Gulma (2021, 44) point out, "Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press)".

As mentioned earlier, the Turabian style is merely the CMS as it applies to research papers. The CMS clarifies the use of spellings, abbreviations, when to capitalise words, how to emphasise writing with italics or other, hyphenation, page formatting, and presentation of data. The whole idea is to instill or formalise consistency in academic writing.

f) Language

There is a significant difference between American and UK English; for consistency, I have learnt that sticking to one language style is good. Technology has made life easy as there are now language checkers to correct grammar, the language of use, spelling, and punctuation. The ACA-401 video recommends running a written essay through the Grammarly premium software for grammar, spelling, and plagiarism checks.

3) CONCLUSION

This essay summarises what I have learnt in the international writing module. With the number of times that I have read the ACA401 course pack and the Turabian Manual of Writing, I am sure that as I progress in this PhD course, I will polish up areas where I am rusty.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Merriam Webster. 2023. "Definition of PUNCTUATION". Accessed 21st February 2023. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/punctuation>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.